

DIFFERENTIATION ON LEARNING ACTIVITY SHEETS IN DEVELOPING THE PROBLEM- SOLVING SKILLS OF GRADE 10 STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

Distance education is an institutional concept of self-directed learning based on education through correspondence courses with an incorporated aspect of communication technology to meet the need for teaching force growth, enhanced professional standards and modernization of teaching methods. Teachers can use learning activity sheets to understand the previous experience, result of learning, and learning process of students; at the same time, they can be used to encourage students to track the progress of their own learning. To support this, this study aimed to determine the perception of the Grade 10 students on the Differentiated Learning Activity Sheets (LAS) in the Development of Problem-Solving Skills in Mathematics. In this study, the descriptive and correlational design of research and random sampling technique was employed with one hundred twenty (120) Grade 10 students as respondents of the study for the school year 2020-2021. The researcher opted to use this research method considering the objective to obtain first hand data from the respondents. The result of the study revealed that there is significant relationship between the learning styles and the problem-solving skills of the students. Integrator has a positive significant relationship to the conceptual understanding and connection of the students. Also, the result shows that there is positive significant relationship between the components of learning activity sheets and the problem-solving skills of the students. Lesson application has a positive significant relationship to the computation/execution of the students. The learning activity sheets developed by the researcher were not proven effective yet in the enhancement of problem-solving skills. The researcher would like to recommend utilizing the developed learning activity sheets considering its learning styles to be executed in an experimental research.

Keywords: Learning Activity Sheet (LAS), Learning Styles, Problem Solving Skills